

STUDYING THE SYNTHESIS OF ANTIOXIDANTS BASED ON GOSSYPOL AND
EPICHLOROHYDRIN

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Abstract. In this paper, the study of a new antioxidant based on gossypol with epichlorohydrin (ECH) was carried out in two ways: in the presence of 1% phosphoric acid and 0.5% alkali solution in a molar ratio of gossypol: alkali=1:2. Obtained in the presence of phosphoric acid, has the following characteristics: it is a homogeneous brown powder, average molecular weight 2300-3500, non-volatile, main component content 99.6% and in an alkaline environment, has the following characteristics: uniform brown powder, average molecular weight 2500-3800, non-volatile, main component content 99.7%. The technological regime of the optimal conditions for the synthesis of gossypol with epichlorohydrin is carried out at a molar ratio of 1:1 in the temperature range of 313–353 K in an alcohol solution. The structure of this compound was confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, spectral and elemental analysis. For comparison, IR spectra of gossypol and its oligomeric derivatives GECH were taken. This obtained oligomer was applied to polyethylene as an antioxidant and improved its mechanical and thermal properties.

Keywords: gossypol, epichlorohydrin, antioxidant, elemental analysis, IR- analysis, ¹H NMR-analysis.

Abbreviations and notation: epichlorohydrin (ECH), gossypol and epichlorohydrin (GECH), gossypol and allyl halides (GAG), gossypol with allylthiourea (GATM), polyethylene (PE), low density polyethylene (LDPE).

Introduction.

Currently, there is an intensive growth in the production and use of polymer materials based on polyolefins and elastomers. At the same time, although they have valuable physicochemical properties, they have a significant drawback: polymer materials based on polyolefins and elastomers are subject to various types of aging under the influence of heat, light, oxygen, etc., and their properties are not always sufficiently stable. Therefore, one of the ways to increase the resistance of polymer materials to heat and oxygen is to introduce antioxidant stabilizers into them.

[1,2]. In recent years, foreign studies have also observed trends in replacing synthetic products with products of natural origin, the raw materials for the production of which are renewable resources [3,4], biological and chemical processes [5], the source of raw materials for the synthesis of which is waste from the wood processing industry (wood and bark of coniferous and deciduous trees) [6,7]. The introduction of a terpene substituent into the aromatic ring of phenols is possible through the interaction of phenols with terpene hydrocarbons, alcohols or halogen derivatives in the presence of acidic catalysts. In the presented work studied the patterns and optimized the conditions for the selective alkylation of phenols with terpenoids in the presence of organoaluminum compounds and the rearrangement of phenylisobornyl ether using various catalysts. Gossypol and some of its derivatives are very active inhibitors of radical reactions (oxidation, polymerization, etc.), it is important to note that the effective concentrations of gossypol are significantly lower than its toxic

level. The hydroxyl groups at position 1 and 1' are relatively inert. Aldehyde groups in the gossypol molecule enhance the inhibitory effect[8-10].

2. Experimental part

2.1. Study of the reaction between gossypol and epichlorohydrin (GECH).

The technology for the production of gossypol with epichlorohydrin (ECH) was carried out in two ways: in the presence of 1% phosphoric acid and 0.5% alkali solution in a molar ratio of gossypol: alkali = 1:2.

The oligomeric product obtained in the presence of phosphoric acid has the following characteristics: it is a homogeneous brown powder, has an average molecular weight of 2300-3500, is non-volatile, main component content of 99.6%.

Reaction scheme according to the first method:

The technology for the synthesis of oligomeric antioxidant based on gossypol and ECH was also carried out in an aqueous solution in the presence of alkali[7]. The reaction is accompanied by the interaction of the hydroxyl groups of gossypol at position 7,7' with the epoxy groups of epichlorohydrin. The reaction scheme can be represented as follows:

Elemental analysis of the synthesized oligomer gave the following result (%): C - 68.8; N - 5.12; O - 24.7. The theoretically calculated elemental composition of HECH based on the above structure is as follows (%): C - 68.1; N - 5.76; O - 25.1.

The reaction of gossypol with epichlorohydrin and allyl compounds is characterized by a complex development of the process, due to the presence of various reactive functional groups.

The technological regime of the optimal conditions for the synthesis of gossypol with epichlorohydrin is carried out at a molar ratio of 1:1 in the temperature range of 313–353 K in an alcohol solution. The kinetics of the process was monitored by changes in the concentration of chlorine ions in the reaction mass as the reaction progressed[8].

Table 2.1.

The influence of the molar ratio of reagents on the composition of the product when preparing the oligomeric antioxidant GECH. (T = 338 K τ = 2 h).

Mole ratio: gossypol:ECH	Yield, %	Average mol. mass (cryoscopy)	Elemental analysis, %			
			Carbon		Hydrogen	
			Calculated	Found	Calculated	Found
3:1	72,3	2380	69,1	68,1	5,7	4,8
2:1	87,7	3450		67,9		5,2
1:1	98,8	4860		68,8		5,1
1:2	85,6	3820		69,3		4,9
1:3	79,2	3340		69,2		4,5

The results presented in Fig. 2.4 show that when gossypol interacts with epichlorohydrin in the presence of 1% phosphoric acid, as in the esterification of other polyhydric alcohols, first there is a rapid interaction of the hydroxyl groups of gossypol with the epoxy groups of epichlorohydrin, the rate of which does not depend on a temperature change of 10-20 °C, then a relatively slow migration of ether formation in the subsequent period.

In this case, the temperature increases to 353 K, as can be seen from Fig. 2.3, leads to an intensification of the oligomerization reaction. Research results show that with increasing temperature, the reaction rate increases by 1.13-1.32 times.

Conclusion

- (i). Methods have been proposed for the production of antioxidants based on gossypol with epichlorohydrin compounds under various conditions and ratios of reagents.
- (ii). Using IR spectroscopy, mass chromatography, ¹H NMR and differential thermal analysis, etc. The inhibitory activity of the synthesized oligomers in PE destruction reactions was studied. It was revealed that the synthesized oligomers based on gossypol prevent thermal-oxidative aging of polymers and are practically superior in efficiency to the antioxidant «Irganox-1010».used in industry.
- (iii). The kinetics of oxygen absorption by the original and stabilized LDPE was studied at different molecular oxygen pressures. It has been established that, along with reactions of inhibition of the polymer oxidation process, the oligomeric antioxidant leads to inhibition of the process of destruction of the polymer composition.
- (iv). According to the obtained results, the amount of antioxidant based on gossypol and epichlorohydrin showed the highest thermal and mechanical strength when the amount was 0.2%.

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